

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DIRECTIONS OF PREPARING PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES FOR THE SOCIALIZATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF A GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: In this thesis, the pedagogical and psychological directions of preparing students for professional activities aimed at socialization through the gender approach are presented.

Key words: Educational system, pedagogy, professional activity, personality, socialization, gender approach

Introduction.

Analysis of pedagogical literature on the problem of personality development shows that there are many definitions of this concept. In the previous paragraph, we emphasized the contribution of Russian teachers of the 19th - 20th centuries to the development of educational theory. B.S. According to Gershunsky, a person consciously or unconsciously evaluates his attitude to life, behavior and actions, focusing on the attitudes and values of the social environment. We analyzed the works of S. T. Shatsky, the founder of environmental pedagogy, about studying and using the educational opportunities of the environment.

Local scientists spoke about the social nature and social function of education, according to them, if it is aimed at solving problems related to life itself, the course of history, education becomes a great force. In the first paragraph, we discussed the characteristics of meta-individuality (psychological characteristics of the relationship of the surrounding people to a certain person) which are, according to the theory, individual and personal names. These situations are reflected in the assessment of the student's individuality by the members of the communication student group. The individuality of young men and women studying in higher education has emotional-personal, value-oriented, reference-metric states. Emotional and personal status is represented by liking or disliking, submissiveness or dominance. Value-oriented status is manifested in the assessment of social and moral characteristics of individuality. The referent-metric status is reflected in the assessment of the reliability of the opinions and judgments of the higher education student. The personality of a

student of higher education can be evaluated not only by the members of the student group, but also can influence real changes in the behavior of the members of the contact group.

We call the internal factors of higher education student personality formation. These are related to the personal characteristics of the student of higher education, his individual characteristics (masculinity, femininity, androgyny) and determine the gnostic and constructive skills of effective thinking. A focus on the external world or the self explains the student's ability to realize his/her gender potential in his/her activities and interpersonal interactions. In this regard, gender socialization is a factor in the development of the personality of a student of higher education.

For our research, A. V. Mudrik's theory about the external factors of personality socialization is of interest. Microfactors are the immediate environment of the student and have a greater influence on the socialization of his personality in the course of everyday life in accordance with the norms and values inherent in this environment. Among them, we consider an educational institution.

For a student, a higher education institution acts as a micro-society. One of the tasks of educating a student's personality is to ensure his targeted socialization. Sociologists V. I. Dobrenkov and A. I. Kravchenko summarized many approaches to defining the concept of "social institution" and came to the conclusion that a social institution is a role system with norms and statuses. It is a combination of customs and rules of conduct, formal and informal organization, a set of norms and institutions regulating a certain sphere of social relations, a separate set of social actions.

Thus, the institution of higher education is formal and informal rules, principles, norms, relationships that regulate the interaction of people in the field of education and training, and organize it into a system of roles and statuses. Due to its normative nature (a set of norms and behavioral patterns), higher education is a tool of social control.

As we noted above, new pedagogical concepts of socialization importance allow the individual to self-determination and self-awareness in society, self-knowledge, self-educate, directs to increase the motivation of self-education. Gender Self-Consciousness, Gender Attitudes, and Personality Gender Behavior Self-Learning, Self-Determination, Self-Management, Self-zi is related to concepts such as self-awareness. These processes describe the activity of a higher education student (boy and girl). According to V. S. Selivanov, the activity of a

higher education student is the independent development of objects of the material and spiritual world. This activity is aimed at changing material and spiritual objects. This is a variety of activities and creativity, as well as purposeful self-education.

A person's desire to fully develop his qualities and abilities, the need for self-improvement, the realization of his potential, the path to a full, rich inner life V. M. Polonsky calls for self-realization. Self-education is a conscious and purposeful activity on the formation and improvement of positive qualities and the elimination of negative qualities.

In our research, we rely on A. S. Belkin's theory of life (vitagen) experience. He calls life (vitagen) experience information (thoughts, feelings, actions experienced by a person) that has become the property of a person. The volume of vitagen data in people of different ages and genders is approximately the same. From a scientific point of view, the process of transferring vitagen information to life experience is carried out in three stages (perception, selection, installation). The process of showing external information to internal information through communication and cognitive activity is called internalization. This phenomenon was discovered and studied almost simultaneously by the Russian researcher L. S. Vygotsky and J. Piaget (Switzerland) at the beginning of the 20th century. E. Durkheim equated this concept with socialization. In this regard, a person's life experience is acquired in the process of socialization.

According to P. Berger and T. Lukman's theory of social construction, a student of higher education is able to make independent decisions and build his behavior independently of current situations in accordance with the assumed gender role. Based on the gender structure discussed in the first paragraph, the formation of the personality of a student (boy or girl) in the process of gender socialization implies the presence of three components in the structure of individuality: cognitive (cognitive), emotional and behavioral. Due to these components, a person acquires value knowledge, value attitude and value behavior. These philosophical categories are currently the subject of pedagogical axiology.

Conclusion.

Thus, we consider gender knowledge (result of knowledge), gender attitude and gender behavior of a student of higher education as the values of education. In the pedagogical dictionary, values are called qualities and characteristics of a person (including social ideals and accepted as relevant representative

standards), which should be achieved as a result of education. Nowadays, it is widely believed that the cultural values of the past should be acquired through knowledge rather than through practice.

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